

Parity violation and magnetic helicity on cosmological scales: from turbulent baryogenesis to galaxy clusters

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Using results of numerical simulations and the data (the CMB photons temperature and polarization anisotropies) obtained by the Planck satellite mission, Atacama Cosmology Telescope, and the South Pole Telescope (SPTpol), it is shown that chaotic/turbulent parity violation localized in long-lived magnetic blobs dominated by magnetic helicity takes place at cosmological leptobaryogenesis. The post-recombination large-scale baryonic matter distribution data obtained by the Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey have also been used to support this conclusion. An analogous phenomenon has also been confirmed (using results of numerical simulations and astrophysical observations) for magnetic fields in galaxy clusters. Despite the vast differences in the values of physical parameters and spatio-temporal scales between the numerical simulations and the cosmic observations, there is a quantitative agreement between the results of the cosmic observations and the numerical simulations within the framework of the distributed chaos notion.

I. INTRODUCTION

Baryogenesis at an earlier stage of the universe's development is one of the main candidates for magnetogenesis. The parity P (reflection symmetry) and charge-parity (CP) violation are a necessary part of the baryogenesis (Sakharov's conditions). Helical magnetic field emerges under these conditions. It should be noted that the electro-weak phase transition can also be involved in generating a helical magnetic field under these conditions (see, for instance, a review [1] and references therein).

The time around the leptobaryogenesis epoch was rather turbulent [2] because about all created baryons and antibaryons (as well as electrons and positrons) were annihilated soon after creation, producing a huge amount of energy. The turbulent magnetic helicity can also be a key for solving the baryon asymmetry problem [2].

The point-wise (more precisely, the patch-like) helicity production is an inherent property of the 3D chaotic/turbulent motion of the plasmas/fluids. In such flows, the helicity appears spontaneously (even in the cases of zero net helicity) in pairs of patches having opposite signs of the helicity so that the net helicity remains zero. This phenomenon takes place in both non-magnetic (kinetic helicity) and magnetic (magnetic helicity) cases [3–7]. In the latter case, a part of the patches is transformed into long-lived magnetic blobs with sign-definite helicity and reduced dissipation [6, 8]. Despite the net helicity is remaining zero the absolute value of the total normalized sum of the sign-definite helicities of the magnetic blobs $|I^\pm|$ ($I^+ = -I^-$) can be used as a measure of spontaneous parity violation (see

Section IV for more detail). In the present paper, we will study how this measure of parity violation is related to a measure of randomness of the chaotic/turbulent magnetic field (some other types of cosmological parity violation built on intrinsic reflection asymmetry of the particles one can find in a recent review [9] and references therein).

The conception of smoothness can be used to quantify the levels of randomness of the chaotic/turbulent dynamical regimes. Indeed, the stretched exponential spectrum

$$E(k) \propto \exp(-(k/k_\beta)^\beta) \quad (1)$$

is a characteristic feature of smooth chaotic dynamics. Here $1 \geq \beta > 0$ and k is the wavenumber.

The value of the $\beta = 1$ characterizes the deterministic chaos (see, for instance, [8, 10–13] and references therein):

$$E(k) \propto \exp(-k/k_c). \quad (2)$$

When $1 > \beta$ the smooth chaotic dynamics can be already non-deterministic; this type of smooth dynamics can be called ‘distributed chaos’ (the term will be clarified below). Another term “soft turbulence” (suggested by [14]) can also be appropriate.

The parameter β could be used as an informative measure of randomization. Namely, the further the value of β is from $\beta = 1$ (which corresponds to the deterministic chaos), the more significant the system's randomization. The smaller parameter β values are considered a precursor of hard turbulence [14].

For non-smooth dynamics (the hard turbulence [14]), the power-law (scaling) spectra are typical. This can happen, in particular, when the magnetic field can be considered as a passive field in a highly turbulent plasma [15].

Many models of baryogenesis were suggested, but there is a consensus to use the CMB data to estimate the

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present-day ratio of the number density of baryons (n_b) to photons (n_γ): $\eta_b = n_b/n_\gamma = 6.12 \times 10^{-10}$ [16]. This is the observational key for the baryogenesis problem (see, for a recent review, Ref. [17] and references therein). The extremely low observed value of the parameter η_b means, in particular, that the number of photons emitted by the recombination process itself is negligible in comparison with the number of photons that came from the previous epochs and were set free at the recombination epoch.

As was already mentioned above, most of the baryons B and antibaryons \bar{B} were annihilated around the baryogenesis epoch, producing a vast amount of energy in the form of photons: $\gamma + \gamma \rightleftharpoons B + \bar{B}$. Since these photons in the post-baryogenesis epoch had insufficient energy to turn into the baryon-antibaryon pairs, most of them survived until the last scattering to become the CMB photons and provide valuable information about the primordial matter-antimatter asymmetry (the η_b , in particular) [18]. Since the leptobaryogenesis, magnetogenesis, the parity violation dominated by the magnetic helicity and the emission of the CMB-to-be photons are strongly interrelated one can expect that the level of the randomness of the magnetic field generated at the leptobaryogenesis epoch could be imprinted on the level of randomness of the temperature of the CMB-to-be photons.

The continuing expansion smoothed out the strong fluctuations characterizing the time around the leptobaryogenesis epoch. At the recombination epoch, only tiny remnants of these fluctuations were present in the matter's motion and CMB photons. The remnants of the randomness, peculiar to the time around the leptobaryogenesis epoch, could also be preserved in the spatial power spectra of the CMB temperature and polarization fluctuations (anisotropies) after the last scattering. Of course, this spectrum is a superposition of the remnant of the turbulent leptobaryogenesis epoch, acoustic oscillations, etc. However, one can hope this remnant can be seen in the observed CMB spectra and provide some information about the physical process at the leptobaryogenesis epoch (see also an interesting discussion of present attempts to approach the problem in a recent paper [19] and references therein). The post-recombination large-scale (cosmological) baryonic matter distribution can also preserve this remnant's imprint.

The observational estimates of the magnetic fields of the galaxy clusters turned out to be much larger than those predicted for the primordial magnetic fields. Therefore, different mechanisms of amplification of the seed magnetic fields (which supposedly came from the primordial stage) by the intensive (chaotic/turbulent) motion of the electrically conducting galaxy cluster plasmas were suggested in the literature. In the galaxy clusters, the

chaotic/turbulent motion could be generated by cluster mergers, structure formation shocks, active galactic nuclei outflows, and the moving galaxy wakes.

Numerous models (numerical simulations) of the galaxy clusters magnetohydrodynamic dynamo were suggested (see, for instance, [20–22] and references therein). Some recent models will be discussed below in detail.

There are certain hints of a parity violation in the magnetized intracluster plasmas. However, it is not clear whether the magnetic helicity in this case has a primordial origin or was generated by the turbulent motion of the intracluster plasmas. Till now, technically, all observables related to the galaxy clusters' magnetic fields are entangled and mixed with other physical characteristics of the magnetized plasmas (electron density, for instance). The observable Faraday rotation maps were used to infer information about the intracluster magnetic field (see, for instance, [23]). It will be shown below that the chaotic/turbulent magnetic field with the parity violation imprints its level of randomness on the Faraday rotation measure (cf the situation with the CMB above).

II. DETERMINISTIC CHAOS IN MAGNETIZED PLASMA

In a recent paper [24] a numerical simulation of a small-scale (fluctuating) dynamo with parameters favorable to deterministic chaos was performed using magnetohydrodynamic (MHD) equations

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (3)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{b}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{b}) + \eta \nabla^2 \mathbf{b}, \quad (4)$$

$$\begin{aligned} \frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} + (\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla) \mathbf{u} = & -\frac{\nabla p}{\rho} + \frac{\mathbf{j} \times \mathbf{b}}{c\rho} \\ & + \nu \left(\nabla^2 \mathbf{u} + \frac{1}{3} \nabla (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}) + 2\mathbf{S} \cdot \nabla \ln \rho \right) + \mathbf{F}, \end{aligned} \quad (5)$$

in a triply-periodic cubic domain. In these equations \mathbf{u} is the plasma velocity field, \mathbf{b} is the divergence-free magnetic field, ρ is the plasma density, p is the plasma pressure, ν is the plasma viscosity, η is the plasma magnetic diffusivity, $\mathbf{j} = (c/4\pi)\nabla \times \mathbf{b}$ was taken for electric current density, c is the speed of light, $S_{ij} = \frac{1}{2}(u_{i,j} + u_{j,i} - \frac{2}{3}\delta_{ij}\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u})$ was taken for the rate-of-strain tensor, and \mathbf{F} is a random delta-correlated in time solenoidal forcing function. An isothermal equation of state, $p = c_s^2 \rho$, was assumed with constant sound speed c_s .

The Reynolds and magnetic Reynolds numbers $Re = Re_m = 1122$, the Mach number $M \approx 0.11$, and the magnetic Prandtl number $Pr_m = 1$. A weak random magnetic field (with zero net flux across the

computational domain) was used as an initial seed field.

Fig. 1 shows the one-dimensional (shell-averaged) magnetic energy spectrum at the saturated stage of the dynamo (the spectral data were taken from Fig. 2 of the paper [24]). The dashed curve is the best fit corresponding to Eq. (2) (deterministic chaos).

III. DISTRIBUTED CHAOS DOMINATED BY MAGNETIC HELICITY

The ideal MHD has three fundamental quadratic invariants: total energy, cross and magnetic helicity [25]. The validity of magnetic helicity conservation increases with the magnetic Reynolds number value Re_m .

The average magnetic helicity density is

$$h_m = \langle \mathbf{a}\mathbf{b} \rangle \quad (6)$$

here \mathbf{a} is the vector potential, $\mathbf{b} = [\nabla \times \mathbf{a}]$ is the fluctuating magnetic field, and $\langle \dots \rangle$ means spatial average (for the fluctuating variables $\langle \mathbf{a} \rangle = \langle \mathbf{b} \rangle = 0$).

The magnetic helicity can be considered as an adiabatic invariant not only in the ideal MHD but also in a weakly dissipative magnetized plasma (see for instance, [26]), that makes it especially interesting for real astrophysical plasmas.

The transition from deterministic chaos to a distributed one can be considered as a randomization. Namely, the change of physical parameters can result in the random fluctuations of the characteristic scale k_c in equation (2). One has to take this phenomenon into account. It can be done using an ensemble averaging

$$E(k) \propto \int_0^\infty \mathcal{P}(k_c) \exp(-k/k_c) dk_c \quad (7)$$

Here, a probability *distribution* $\mathcal{P}(k_c)$ describes the random fluctuations of k_c . This is the rationale behind the name ‘distributed chaos’.

For the magnetic field dynamics dominated by the magnetic helicity the scaling relationship between characteristic values of k_c and B_c based on dimensional considerations

$$B_c \propto |h_m|^{1/2} k_c^{1/2} \quad (8)$$

can be used to find the probability distribution $\mathcal{P}(k_c)$.

The value of B_c can be taken half-normally distributed $\mathcal{P}(B_c) \propto \exp(-(B_c^2/2\sigma^2))$ ([27]). It is a normal distribution with a zero mean, which is truncated to have a nonzero probability density function for positive values of its argument only. For instance, if B is a normally distributed random variable, then the variable $B_c = |B|$

FIG. 1. Magnetic energy spectrum at the saturated stage of fluctuating MHD dynamo for the Mach number $M \approx 0.11$ (numerical simulation).

is half-normally distributed ([28]).

From Eq. (8) we then obtain

$$\mathcal{P}(k_c) \propto k_c^{-1/2} \exp(-k_c/4k_\beta) \quad (9)$$

It is the chi-squared probability distribution where k_β is a new constant).

Substituting Eq. (9) into Eq. (7) one obtains

$$E(k) \propto \exp(-(k/k_\beta)^{1/2}) \quad (10)$$

IV. SPONTANEOUS BREAKING OF LOCAL REFLECTION SYMMETRY

For chaotic/turbulent flows with global reflection symmetry the net magnetic helicity is equal to zero, whereas the point-wise magnetic helicity is not (because of the spontaneous breaking of the local reflection symmetry, see Introduction). The spontaneous local symmetry breaking in such flows is accompanied by the emergence of the blobs with non-zero magnetic helicity [6, 8, 25, 29]. The magnetic surfaces of these blobs can be defined by the boundary conditions: $\mathbf{b}_n \cdot \mathbf{n} = 0$, where \mathbf{n} is a unit vector normal to the boundary of the blob. The magnetic helicity (and its adiabatic conservation) suppresses energy dissipation in such blobs considerably [29], that results in the long-term survival of these blobs in chaotic/turbulent environments.

The sign-definite magnetic helicity of the j-blob can be defined as

$$H_j^\pm = \int_{V_j} (\mathbf{a}(\mathbf{x}, t) \cdot \mathbf{b}(\mathbf{x}, t)) d\mathbf{x} \quad (11)$$

where (‘+’ or ‘-’) denotes the blob’s helicity sign. The H_j^\pm is an adiabatic invariant [25].

FIG. 2. Magnetic energy spectra at the saturated stage of the fluctuating MHD dynamo for the Mach numbers $M = 0.1$ (bottom) and $M = 10$ (top). Numerical simulations.

Then we can consider the total sign-definite adiabatic invariant

$$I^\pm = \lim_{V \rightarrow \infty} \frac{1}{V} \sum_j H_j^\pm \quad (12)$$

The summation takes into account the blobs with a certain sign only ('+' or '-'), and V is the total volume.

The adiabatic invariant I^\pm defined by Eq. (12) can be used instead of the averaged magnetic helicity density h_m in the above estimate Eq. (8) for the special case of the local reflection symmetry breaking

$$B_c \propto |I^\pm|^{1/2} k_c^{1/2} \quad (13)$$

and the spectrum Eq. (10) can also be obtained for this case.

In recent papers [30, 31] numerical simulations similar to that considered in Section II were performed (the net magnetic helicity was also negligible), but in these simulations the large Mach number $M = 10$ was achieved. Figure 2 shows the magnetic energy spectra computed in these numerical simulations. The spectral data shown in this figure were taken from Fig. C4 of the Ref. [31]. While for the small Mach number $M = 0.1$ the bottom dashed curve in Fig. 2 indicates the exponential spectrum Eq. (2) (deterministic chaos, cf Fig. 1), for the large Mach number $M = 10$ the top dashed curve indicates a stretched exponential spectrum Eq. (10) with $\beta = 1/2$. This indicates the distributed chaos dominated by magnetic helicity, i.e. the spontaneous breaking of local reflection symmetry.

In a recent paper [32] numerical simulations of magnetized ultrarelativistic plasma in an expanding flat universe at the radiation-dominated epoch after the electro-weak phase transition were performed using the comov-

FIG. 3. Magnetic energy spectra in an expanding flat universe at the radiation-dominated epoch after the electro-weak phase transition (numerical simulations). The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

ing equations

$$\frac{\partial \ln \rho}{\partial t} = -\frac{4}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \ln \rho) + \frac{1}{\rho} [\mathbf{u} \cdot (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta \mathbf{J}^2], \quad (14)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{u}}{\partial t} = -\mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \mathbf{u} + \frac{\mathbf{u}}{3} (\nabla \cdot \mathbf{u} + \mathbf{u} \cdot \nabla \ln \rho) + \frac{2}{\rho} \nabla \cdot (\rho \nu \mathbf{S}) - \frac{1}{4} \nabla \ln \rho - \frac{\mathbf{u}}{\rho} [\mathbf{u} \cdot (\mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}) + \eta \mathbf{J}^2] + \frac{3}{4\rho} \mathbf{J} \times \mathbf{B}, \quad (15)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} - \eta \mathbf{J} + \mathbf{F}). \quad (16)$$

The random electromotive force \mathbf{F} simulates the generation of magnetic fields and was activated for a short duration (10% of the Hubble time). Two forcing cases were considered: fully helical and with negligible helicity. The simulations were performed in a periodic cubic box. The magnetic Prandtl number $Pr_m = \nu/\eta = 1$.

The magnetic energy spectra shown in Fig. 3 were computed at the time when the magnetic energy density reached its maximum. The spectral data were taken from Figs. 2 and 3 of the Ref. [32]. The dashed curves indicate the magnetic helicity-dominated spectrum Eq. (10) for both cases: with fully helical (top) and non-helical (bottom) forcing. In the latter case, one can recognize the spontaneous parity violation caused by the chaotic/turbulent dynamics of the magnetized primordial plasma.

The above-discussed macroscopic mechanism of the chaotic/turbulent parity breaking and magnetic helicity generation can also boost the microscopic mechanisms of the parity breaking and magnetic helicity generation. Let us consider an example.

In a recent paper [33], the generation of the large-scale magnetic field in relativistic fermion's plasmas due to a

FIG. 4. Magnetic energy spectra in relativistic fermions' plasmas generated due to a nonzero chiral chemical potential fluctuations μ_5 (numerical simulations). The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

nonzero chiral chemical potential fluctuations μ_5 (at initial $\langle\mu_5\rangle = 0$) were studied using direct numerical simulation. The nonzero chiral potential appears in spatial areas of plasma where the chemical potentials of right and left-handed fermions are different. The chiral magnetohydrodynamic equations were used for this purpose

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} = \nabla \times [\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B} - \eta (\nabla \times \mathbf{B} - \mu_5 \mathbf{B})], \quad (17)$$

$$\rho \frac{D\mathbf{u}}{Dt} = (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) \times \mathbf{B} - \nabla p + \nabla \cdot (2\nu \rho \mathbf{S}), \quad (18)$$

$$\frac{D\rho}{Dt} = -\rho \nabla \cdot \mathbf{u}, \quad (19)$$

$$\frac{D\mu_5}{Dt} = \mathcal{D}_5(\mu_5) + \lambda \eta [\mathbf{B} \cdot (\nabla \times \mathbf{B}) - \mu_5 \mathbf{B}^2], \quad (20)$$

where λ is the chiral feedback parameter, the hyperdiffusion operator $\mathcal{D}_5(\mu_5) = -\mathcal{D}_5 \nabla^4 \mu_5$. Unlike the standard MHD, here one can speak about the conservation of total chirality $\langle \mathbf{A} \cdot \mathbf{B} \rangle + 2\langle \mu_5 \rangle / \lambda$ (for $\langle \mu_5 \rangle = 0$ it is the magnetic helicity). The isothermal equation of state $p = \rho c_s^2$ relates pressure and density.

The equations were numerically solved in a periodic spatial box. Initial fluctuations of the chiral chemical potential μ_5 were taken as a Gaussian noise with spectrum $E_5(t_0) \propto k^{-n} \exp(-k^2/k_{\text{cut}}^2)$. The initial $\langle \mu_5 \rangle = 0$, and the initial magnetic helicity was negligible. The initial velocity field was absent, whereas initial (seed) magnetic field fluctuations were small. The dynamo was activated on small spatial scales due to the initial fluctuations of the chiral chemical potential, the Lorentz forces generated the magnetically dominated chaotic/turbulent plasma motion, and the inverse cascade (related to the magnetic helicity conservation) supposedly produced the large-scale magnetic field.

We will consider the runs performed with $n = 1, 2$. Figure 4 shows the magnetic energy spectra computed

FIG. 5. Power spectrum of CMB temperature fluctuations: Planck + ACT measurements. The insert shows the same spectral data (Planck) in the form emphasizing the baryon acoustic peaks in the linear-linear scales.

when the peak of the dynamo magnetic energy had the size of the computational box. The spectral data for Fig. 4 were taken from Fig. 4 of the Ref. [33].

The dashed curves indicate correspondence to the stretched exponential Eq. (10).

V. SIGNATURE OF THE PARITY VIOLATION AT THE LEPTO-BARYOGENESIS EPOCH IN THE CMB SPECTRA

A. CMB temperature fluctuations

Figure 5 shows a combined (Planck+ACT) power spectrum of CMB temperature fluctuations obtained by the Planck mission and Atacama Cosmology Telescope (ACT). The CMB data shown in Fig. 5 were cleaned from the foreground by the Planck and ACT teams. The spectral data were taken from the corresponding sites [34, 35]. The ACT data were used for $kR > 1900$.

At the Planck and ACT sites the spectral data are given for the angular power spectra C_l vs the spherical multipole (or spherical harmonic degree) l . Using a 2D plane wavevector approximation [36] the spherical multipole l can be related to a wavenumber $k_l = \sqrt{l(l+1)}/R$, where R is the sphere's radius, and the azimuthally averaged 2D power spectral density $E(k_l) \approx R^2 C_l / \pi$ [36].

The dashed curve indicates correspondence to the stretched exponential spectrum Eq. (10) (the vertical dotted arrow indicates position of $k_\beta R$). With the assumption that the magnetic field at the lepto/baryogenesis epoch imprints its level of randomization on the temperature of the CMB-to-be photons (see Introduction), Fig. 5 can be considered as an indication that the remnant spectrum from the lepto/baryogenesis epoch can indeed be seen in the CMB spectrum.

FIG. 6. Power spectra of CMB temperature fluctuations: the ACTPol measurements in 98 and 150 GHz channels.

FIG. 7. Power spectra of B-mode of CMB polarization fluctuations: the South Pole Telescope (SPTpol) measurements.

FIG. 8. Power spectra of B-mode of CMB polarization fluctuations: the 150 GHz channel of the SPTpol (circles) and the Λ CDM multi-parametric model (red curve). The best fit with Eq. (2) (the dashed straight line) was performed for the Λ CDM model.

The waviness of the spectrum can be related to the baryon acoustic oscillations as one can see from the insert in Figure 5, where the same spectral data (Planck) has been shown in the form $D_l = l(l+1)C_l/2\pi$ vs l in the linear-linear scales. This presentation is usually used to emphasize the baryon acoustic peaks (at the large values $l \approx kR$).

The randomization with $\beta = 1/2$ provides evidence of the parity violation and the magnetic helicity domination over the emission of the CMB-to-be photons at the lepto/baryogenesis epoch (at least for the middle and small scales).

It is also interesting to look at the CMB temperature spectra obtained using ACTPol 98 and 150 GHz channels. Figure 6 shows these spectra on the log-linear scales. The spectral data were taken from the site [37] for the ‘deep’ files (see also Ref. [38]). The dashed curve shows the best fit corresponding to Eq. (10) for the 150 GHz channel (for the 98 GHz channel, the best fit is about the same). The value of $k_\beta R \approx 16.5$ corresponds to that used in Fig. 5 for the combined Planck+ACT data.

B. B-mode of CMB polarization fluctuations

In a Ref. [39] a spin-2 decomposition of the polarization tensor (vector) was suggested. In this technique, the polarization tensor (vector) is decomposed using two rotationally invariant scalar (E) and pseudo-scalar (B) quantities. The B-mode has magnetic-type parity.

The B-mode power spectrum observations are usually used to test theoretical/numerical models of the primordial magnetic fields.

In a recent paper [40], results of measurements made with the South Pole Telescope (SPTpol) were reported. This paper used 500 deg² of the SPTpol data set obtained for two frequency channels: 95 and 150 GHz. It is the most precise data for the CMB B-mode at large values of l at present.

Figure 7 shows B-mode bandpowers reported in the Ref. [40] for the two frequency channels. The spectral data were taken from Table II of the Ref. [40]. The dashed curves indicate the best fit corresponding to Eq. (10) (the distributed chaos with $\beta = 1/2$) for the 95 GHz channel (top curve) and the best fit corresponding to Eq. (2) (the deterministic chaos) for the less powered channel 150 GHz (bottom curve), cf Fig. 2.

One can see that the results obtained with the 95 GHz channel are in accordance with the CMB temperature measurements (Fig. 5). Since the results obtained with the less powered channel 150 GHz correspond to the de-

FIG. 9. Sketch illustrating the idea of imprinting the primordial baryon spatial distribution on the baryon matter distribution, which can now be observed in the sky (courtesy of C. Blake and S. Moorfield).

terministic chaos, it is interesting to compare them with the well-known Λ CDM multi-parametric model [41]. Figure 8 shows such a comparison in the log-linear scales. The best fit with Eq. (2) (the dashed straight line) was performed for the Λ CDM model.

It should be noted that the compact attractors in phase space corresponding to the deterministic chaos are usually determined by dissipation effects, whereas the distributed chaos (with $\beta = 1/2$) dominated by the adiabatic (quasi-ideal) helical invariant I^\pm should have a sufficient power to overcome the dissipation (cf Fig. 7 and Fig. 2).

VI. SIGNATURE OF THE PARITY VIOLATION AT THE LEPTO-BARYOGENESIS EPOCH IN THE BARYON OSCILLATION SPECTROSCOPIC SURVEY

The processes in the epochs preceding the recombination imprinted themselves not only on the radiation but also on the surviving baryons, which were tightly coupled with the photons. The baryon acoustic oscillations -BAO (which caused the waviness of the CMB spectrum in Fig. 5) were imprinted on the baryon matter distribution, which can now be observed in the sky. The traces of the BAO in the clustering of galaxies can be used as a ruler in measuring the distance-redshift relations. This method was employed for constructing the famous Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey - BOSS, mapping the spatial distribution of luminous red galaxies and quasars [42, 43]. Figure 9 (adapted from the site [44], courtesy of C. Blake and S. Moorfield) shows a sketch illustrating the idea.

The power spectrum of a distribution of points (galaxies for a galactic sample) can be defined as the Fourier

FIG. 10. Power spectrum of baryon matter distribution computed for the Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey.

transform of the two-point correlation function:

$$P(\mathbf{k}) = \frac{n}{(2\pi)^{3/2}} \int \xi(\mathbf{r}) e^{i\mathbf{k}\mathbf{r}} d^3\mathbf{r} \quad (21)$$

where n is the mean density. It seems simple but it is very difficult to calculate the real-space matter spectrum from a 3D galaxy survey due to survey geometry effects, effects of light-to-mass bias, redshift-space distortions, and many other practical complications.

Figure 10 shows an isotropic $P(k)$ spectrum calculated using the data of the Baryon Oscillation Spectroscopic Survey (containing about one million galaxies). The spectral data were taken from the site [42] (see also Ref. [43]). The DR11 sample of the BOSS covers 8500 square degrees at the redshift range $0.2 < z < 0.7$.

The dashed curve in Fig. 10 indicates the best fit by Eq. (10).

VII. MAGNETIC FIELD IN GALAXY CLUSTERS AND FARADAY ROTATION MAPS

A. Numerical simulations

The numerical models (simulations) not only allow a better understanding of the relevant physical processes but they become indispensable because of a principal difficulty of measurements (observations) of galaxy clusters' magnetic fields. Till now, technically, all observables related to the galaxy clusters' magnetic fields are entangled and mixed with other physical characteristics of the magnetized plasmas (electron density, for instance).

In a paper [45] spectra of the magnetic energy and corresponding spectra of the Faraday rotational measure maps were computed in the framework of the standard

FIG. 11. Magnetic energy spectra computed for the collisional (top) and collisionless (bottom) magnetohydrodynamics. The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

(collisional) magnetohydrodynamics and in the framework of a collisionless MHD model (which is expected to be more appropriate to the magnetized and weakly collisional intracluster plasma). This model is based on the dynamic equations

$$\frac{\partial \rho}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho \mathbf{u}) = 0, \quad (22)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho \mathbf{u})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot \left[\rho \mathbf{u} \mathbf{u} + \left(\mathbf{P} + \frac{\mathbf{B}^2}{8\pi} \right) \mathbf{I} - \frac{\mathbf{B} \mathbf{B}}{4\pi} \right] = \mathbf{f}, \quad (23)$$

$$\frac{\partial \mathbf{B}}{\partial t} - \nabla \times (\mathbf{u} \times \mathbf{B}) = 0, \quad (24)$$

where the pressure tensor is

$$\mathbf{P} = p_{\perp} \mathbf{I} + (p_{\parallel} - p_{\perp}) \hat{\mathbf{b}} \hat{\mathbf{b}}, \quad (25)$$

here $p_{\perp} = c_{\perp}^2 \rho$, $p_{\parallel} = c_{\parallel}^2 \rho$, $\hat{\mathbf{b}} = \mathbf{B}/|\mathbf{B}|$, and c_{\perp} and c_{\parallel} are the sound speeds perpendicular and parallel to the magnetic field \mathbf{B} , correspondingly.

The paper's authors [45] reported some indications of a small-scale (fluctuation) dynamo in work for their models.

Figure 11 shows the spectra of magnetic energy computed for the collisional (top) and collisionless (bottom) magnetohydrodynamics with a weak uniform external magnetic field $B_{ext} = 0.1$ and sound speed $c_{snd} = 0.1$ for collisional and $c_{\parallel} = 0.1$, $c_{\perp} = 0.05$ for collisionless cases (in terms of Ref. [45]). The spectral data were taken from Figs. 6a and 6b of the paper [45]. The dashed curves indicate the best fit by the stretched exponential Eq. (10).

One can see that for both models interpretation of the spectral data for magnetic energy using the notion of the distributed chaos dominated by magnetic helicity Eq. (10) is in good agreement with the results of the

FIG. 12. Power spectra of the Faraday rotational measure maps computed for the collisional (top) and collisionless (bottom) magnetohydrodynamics. The spectra are vertically shifted for clarity.

FIG. 13. Intracluster magnetic power spectra for the northern radio lobe of Hydra A for two values of the inclination angles (between the line of sight and the northern lobe) $\theta = 45^\circ$ (top) and $\theta = 30^\circ$ (bottom).

numerical simulations.

Figure 12 shows the power spectra of the Faraday rotational measure maps corresponding to Fig. 11. The spectral data were taken from Figs 12a,c of the paper [45]. The dashed curves indicate the best fit by the stretched exponential Eq. (10).

One can see that the magnetic field imprints its level of randomization on the Faraday maps. Therefore, the observational Faraday rotation measure maps could be used to obtain this information about the magnetic fields.

FIG. 14. Radially averaged power spectrum of a Faraday rotation measure map for the galaxy cluster A119 .

B. Observations

In a paper [23] the Faraday rotation maps of the northern radio lobe of Hydra A (a cool core galaxy cluster) were analyzed with a Bayesian maximum likelihood analysis to infer the intracluster magnetic field power spectrum. Figure 13 shows the magnetic power spectra for two values of the inclination angles (between the line of sight and the northern lobe) $\theta = 45^\circ$ (top) and $\theta = 30^\circ$ (bottom). The spectral data were taken from Fig. 7 of the paper [23].

The dashed curve indicates the best fit by the stretched exponential Eq. (10) (cf previous section).

Figure 14 shows the radially averaged power spectrum of a Faraday rotation measure map for the galaxy cluster A119 (the spectral data were taken from Fig. 10d of paper [46]). This galaxy cluster is located in a region with a rather low Galactic rotation measure and consists of three extended radio galaxies. These galaxies are located at different projected distances (170, 453, and 1515 kpc) from the cluster center and the radio sources are highly polarized.

The dashed curve indicates the best fit by the stretched exponential Eq. (10).

VIII. CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

A parity violation mechanism related to the spontaneous appearance of non-zero magnetic helicity in the long-lived magnetic blobs at the time around the turbulent lepto/baryogenesis has been suggested, and its traces in the CMB radiation (Planck, ACT and SPTpol measurements) and the post-recombination baryonic matter distribution (BOSS observations) have been discussed.

Analogous mechanism related to the primordial seed magnetic field amplification in galaxy clusters and its traces in the Faraday rotation measure observations have also been suggested and discussed. The results of relevant numerical simulations have been used to support this approach.

The generalized (normalized) net magnetic helicity I^\pm Eq. (12) has been used as a measure of the parity violation for the case of zero net magnetic helicity. The level of randomization (characterized by the parameter $\beta = 1/2$, see Introduction) of the primordial magnetic field has been related to the measure of parity violation I^\pm . Then, it has been argued that this level of randomization was imprinted on the CMB-to-be photons' temperature and polarization at the time around the turbulent lepto/baryogenesis, and a remnant of this level of randomization remains in the CMB photons' temperature and polarization at the last scattering surface, Figs. 5-8.

The waviness in the CMB temperature spectrum can be related to the primordial acoustic oscillations (insert in Fig. 5). The idea that the baryon acoustic oscillations imprinted themselves on the observed baryonic matter distribution underlies the BOSS project (see Fig. 9 and [43]). Therefore, one can expect that the level of randomization of the baryonic matter distribution observed by the BOSS will be the same $\beta = 1/2$ (see Fig. 10).

An analogous phenomenon takes place at the primordial seed magnetic field amplification in galaxy clusters, and its traces are found in the Faraday rotation measurement observations (see Figs. 11-14).

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